

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

ZEB34A A phase II Clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product Data Management Plan

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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I. Data areas and data types

This CTIMP involves the capture of electronic healthcare data at the site by research nurses. This data will be stored on electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs), including data such as blood results, demographics, pharmacovigilance data, treatment records and quality of life assessments.

II. Standards and metadata

Standard metadata will be produced for this clinical trial. The metadata files uniquely identify each data object within the study CRFs and will be replicated and structured consistently across to the sub-study to enhance its discoverability and reusability. Methodologies for statistical analyses performed will be documented thoroughly. All outputs of this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources design for these purposes.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Data in this project comes from a single source – the ZEB34A clinical trial, hosted by the University. Data curated in the ZEB34A trial are not publicly available yet due to ongoing research.

IV. Secondary use

Data Controllership is held by the University Clinical Trials Unit, whereby the University is designated Sponsor and data controller. The research consent model for this trial enables the future use of the data generated in this trial, whereby future use (including secondary analysis datasets) will only be provided as fully anonymised format and following the publication of primary analyses.

V. Methods for data sharing

The ZEB34A trial is ongoing and therefore data cannot be shared until the primary analysis has been performed and the main publication made. Following publication, we intend to publish the data from this sub-study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings, cited as the main ZEB34A clinical trial listed within this publicly accessible registry. ISRCTN registry attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number, which may be referenced in future citations.

VI. Proprietary data

Participants of the ZEB34A clinical trial provided consent for anonymised data to be shared with approved projects for future research. Until the primary analyses have been performed, no datasets will be released.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

The final pseudonymised dataset will be prepared for long-term storage, with consideration to conversion and future use. Data will be stored in .csv format as an open, standard, interchangeable and longer-lasting format, thus maximising the potential for future utility. For long-term digital preservation, the University data centres archive data in open and standard formats.